

Generalization and Relation of Probabilistic Models to Finite Automata

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ABSTRACT

We give the definition of the relation of probabilistic models towards construction of finite automata recognizing certain patterns for the given probability set.

Keywords: automata, probability, model, regular languages.

INTRODUCTION

The probability automata is a long-standing question [1, 2, 3, 4], recently the question was raised again [5].

RELATION

We define the function over the languages f :

$$f : P(\dots) \rightarrow E.$$

As it can be seen the above function is defined for the probability of events which can be terminal or non-terminal as well as the symbols in regular language defined by the alphabet E .

$$f(a) = L(a), f(a|b) = L(a+b), f(a|(b, c, d)) = L(b \cdot c \cdot d \cdot a), f(a \wedge b) = L(a) \wedge L(b).$$

The above notation can be used in proving and simulation of probability events on finite automata.

CONCLUSION

We have defined the general function which can be used in defining the regular languages and giving the definition of the regular probabilistic languages.

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